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IMPLEMENTING ALTERNATE TECHNOLOGIES TO IMPROVE THE POWER HANDLING CAPACITY OF ALL SI-MEMS PHASE SHIFTERS

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Abstract:

This proposal paper analyze and suggest the alternate methods to reduce the heat dissipation and power consumption of MEMS phase shifters while they are being used in the real time environment i.e., in a closed loop operation. So many advancements in the MEMS technology make the MEMS production very effective, but still there are some drawbacks in its structure and in its performance, which pulls the system efficiency to down. Self and mutual inductions are the two major run time defects which affects the performances of the MEMS devices and increases its power consumption when there is a physical data link between two blocks. If the proper steps are taken then, the measurement results can range up to 40dBm at 75 GHz or even more. Hence by using alternate methods for the communication between the two blocks using PIC 16f778 controller we can reduce the temperature rise in all Si-phase shifters, which is 20-30 times lesser than the conventional MEMS phase shifters. Also by implementing this idea we can reduce the fabrication cost and we can make a great revolution in the field of embedded systems.

Key terms: --- Microwave, phase shifters, optic fiber, radio frequency micro electro mechanical systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless communication is nowadays widely utilized in many high-performance devices and remote sensing systems, comprising radar sensors based on phased antenna arrays. This wireless communication can be enabled by using some electro-magnetic waves such as microwaves and radio waves.

Using radio frequency MEMS phase shifters exhibits near ideal behavior, consisting very low losses, high linearity, and ease of integration and miniaturization. In the conventional type, the MEMS have two types of communication networks, which are switched line network and distributed MEMS transmission line (DMTL). Using switched line networks we may gain higher performance up to 40GHz, which on exceeding more may leads to higher losses. Using DMTL we may fetch considerable performance even at millimeter wave frequencies.

The above mentioned conventional types of MEMS have very limited power handling utility, because thin movable metallic bridges are used in both the cases. At high signal power, especially at greater frequencies, we can observe

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the rising induced current density in the thin metallic bridge, which also may result high temperature rise in the free standing bridges. Usually the metallic bridge is made up of gold which even on slight C leads to the physical degradation. In order to avoid the flaws the designers decided to use platinum, aluminum, and molybdenum which have the higher physical retaining property, but they will suffer RF losses because of lower electrical conductivity, as compared with gold.

In these circumstances what this paper would like to convey is, instead of using the transmission lines and metallic bridges, we can implement wireless communication or optic communication between the blocks which may drastically reduces the occurrence of run time flaws in the MEMS. By comparing this with the conventional types may infer that power handling is not limited by structures and transmission media but only by the heat sink capabilities of the substrate, which ensures the MEMS phase shifters technology for high power reliability applications. This concept is however less suitable for lower frequencies. But by implementing this technique we can rise the life time of MEMS which on other side may leads to the lower production costs in the field of mechatronics and in robotics.

II STUDY OF CONVENTIONAL DESIGNS

AND PHASE SHIFTERS

The diagrammatic representation of the conventional types and the proposal type is shown clearly in the Fig.1. Fig. 1(a) or for the capacitive loading of the coplanar waveguide (CPW) as in the DMTL concept in Fig. 1(b). The thin metallic bridges employed in these conventional designs are the bottleneck in terms of power handling. The bridges must be relatively thin for acceptable actuation voltages, which results in high current densities at elevated power levels, particularly at higher frequencies.

(b) conventional concept: DMTL phase shifters

c) This work-- dielectric block

These high power densities, in connection with the poor thermal conductivity of the free standing bridges to the substrate heat sink, result in a large temperature rise of bridges. The electrical resistance of the gold bridges also increases with the temperature and the frequency, resulting in a much higher temperature rise, particularly in the downstate position of the gold bridges. Even at slightly elevated temperatures of 80 °C, the mechanical elasticity of the bridges (particularly when made of gold, which is the most commonly used material) degrades, resulting in the altered actuation behavior and the drastically limited lifetime. At even higher temperatures, significant thermo mechanical deformations of the gold bridges occur, resulting in serious reliability issues including permanent plastic deformation, thermal-strain-induced buckling, creeping, or even melting of the gold bridges.

Furthermore, most of the MEMS phase shifters are fabricated on quartz or glass to minimize substrate losses but offer bad thermal properties. For example, fused quartz has approximately 111-times lower thermal conductivity, as compared with silicon .Thus, the fused-quartz substrate acts as a bad heat sink for the thin movable gold bridges. This also greatly limits the power handling in this paper are fabricated with a CPW transmission line, the implementation with a micro strip line was studied ,and the results are similar to the CPW design.

III BRIEF STUDY ON RF PERFORMANCE AND MEMS WORTHY CHARACTERISTICS

While using the conventional MEMS, due to drastic rise in temperature it exhibits the irregular RF performance and non-linear characteristics. For a 5.51-mm-long 4.25-bit binary-coded phase shifter .Prototype, the return and insertion losses at the nominal Frequency of 75 GHz are -17 and -3.5 dB, respectively. For the whole W-band, it performs with a return loss better than -15 dB and an insertion loss better than -4 dB. These data Correspond to phase-shifter efficiency values of -0.82 dB/bit and 71.1° /bit at 75 GHz, and -0.94 dB/bit and 98.3° /bit at 110 GHz. This proposed concept is exceptional broadband even outside the W-band. The measured phase error from 10 to 110 GHz is better than 3% for all states, and the linearity is excellent with a measured third-order intercept point of 49 dBm. The mechanical reliability of the dielectric-block phase shifter was evaluated.

Fig. 2. High-power measurement setup with infrared microscope and large signal Network analyzer with input power up to 43 dBm (20 W) at 3 GHz

IV. POWER HANDLING MEASUREMENTS AND ANALYSIS FOR HARDWARE DESIGNING.

A. Automatic-gain -controlled measurement setup

The block diagram of the high-power measurement setup is shown in Fig. 2. The setup is composed of a signal generator connected to a 3-GHz tunable solid-state power amplifier with a maximum tuning range up to 46 dBm (40 W). A circulator is employed in the setup to protect the power amplifier from the reflected signal; thus, the reflected power is dissipated at a 50-Ω termination connected at the other port of the circulator. Four directional couplers are required to detect the transmitted and reflected signals at the input (a1 and b1) and output (a2 and b2) ports of the phase shifter. These parameters are used for controlling and stabilizing the gain of the power amplifier to the required RF power level at the input port of the device under test (DUT) by the large-signal network analyzer. Although the direct-current (dc) blockage during the actuation is not required in the setup since the dc probes were launched on the spring anchor and the CPW ground, unlike most of the conventional designs where the actuation

probes are placed on the signal line and ground, the bias-tee circuit was placed in the setup to protect the measurement system from all possible dc leakages. The dielectric-block phase shifter is placed on a temperature-controlled chuck to establish the temperature stabilization of the DUT to 65 °C, protecting the measurement environment from the unwanted external heat source. Finally, another 50-Ω load is required to dissipate the power at the end terminal of the measurement setup.

Fig. 3. Top-view infrared-microscope pictures of the 45°, 30° , and 15°single-stage phase shifters.

B. Thermal Characterization under High RF Power Up to 43 dBm (20 W) at 3 GHz

The thermal measurements of the $7 \times 45^\circ$ linear-coded multistage phase shifter are presented in Fig. 4. For all silicon blocks in the upstate position, the peak-temperature rise along the y-y_ line is 11.06 °C and 10.63 °C when the fifth-stage silicon block is actuated, i.e., pulled down. The hottest spots occur on the signal line of the CPW, which are determined by the skin effect and the power level of the input RF signal. As shown in Fig. 4(b), the actuated silicon block performs as an additional heat sink of the devices, resulting in a temperature rise of approximately 3 °C lower at the corners of the silicon block, as compared when it is in the upstate position.

C. Analysis over Simulation Results and Automatic Gain Controlled High Power Management.

The measurement results at 3 GHz with the signal power of 40 dBm (10 W) in Fig. 3 were mapped by the RF/electro thermal simulations (CST Studio Suite), and the simulation parameters were calibrated from both microwave and thermal measurement results. Thus, heat can flow from the heat source (signal line) through the middle of the movable silicon block and flows to the heat sink (substrate) at the edges where the temperature is slightly lower. Therefore, the temperature-rise distribution decreased from 12 °C in the middle of the silicon block to 8 °C at the edges. To fully correlate the thermal simulations with the infrared measurements, it must be understood that silicon is

switched-line concepts). The geometry and material parameters of the switched-line and DMTL W-band phase shifters for the RF and electro Thermal simulation models are taken from [7] and [10], respectively, in an effort to reproduce the RF performance of state-of-the-art designs of these conventional MEMS phase shifter.

For the recently reported dielectric block phase shifter (45° stage), the maximum temperature rise is only 30 °C. Even if a silicon substrate, offering a better heat sink, would be used for the conventional phase shifters, which, however, would drastically degrade their RF performance by 2.5–4 dB in the W-band, the temperature increase would still be 330 °C and 120 °C for the switched line and DMTL designs, respectively (11 and 4 times more than the novel design, respectively). For gold, which is a very common material for fabricating the bridges of the conventional phase shifters, the peak temperatures should be kept below an absolute temperature of 80 °C in order not to degrade the metallic bridges.

a) conventional concept: switched line phase shifters

b) conventional concept: DMTL phase shifters

Fig. 5. Simulated temperature rise at 75 GHz and 40 dBm of (a) a 45 single-stage dielectric-block phase shifter on high-resistivity Si substrate, (b) a single switch of switched-line phase shifter on quartz, and (c) on high-resistivity silicon substrate; and (d) a 45 stage of a DMTL phase shifter on quartz and (e) on silicon substrate, respectively.

TEMP Vs. POWER :(Simulated graphical o/p)

Fig. 6. Simulated peak-temperature rises of the three MEMS phase-shifter concepts at a signal power from 0.1 to 10 W (20–40 dBm) at 75 GHz.

TABLE I: COMPARATIVE FIGURE-OF-MERIT

Aspects	DB with alternate wireless communication(this concept)	DMTL (conventional)	Switched line (conventional)
Substrate used	Si*	Glass /quartz	Glass/quartz /GAAs
Structural material	Si*	Metals(Au)	Metals(Au)
Thermal conductivity	Very good	Poor	Poor
Power dissipation	Extremely low	Very high	Extremely high
Temp rise @high power	Very low	Very high	Extremely high
Overall high power handling	Excellent	Very bad @high freq	Extremely bad
Peak temp. rise	30°C	300 °C	650°C
Limitation of power handling	t-line	Metallic bridge**	MEMS switches**
Plastic deformation temperature of the MEMS	Very high	Very low	Very low
RF losses for whole W-band	Low	Low /moderate	High
MEMS reliability @ high power	Very good	Moderate	Low /moderate

APPLICATIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE.

Using this concept, we can avail user friendly environment for people working in high temperature and pressure workplaces. This can save valuable human lives in very critical cases. This technique can be implemented in large scale industries.

We can use this concept in manufacturing the Robots and automation devices to acquire higher efficiency and low power consumption which makes the production cost very much affordable even to the lay-man. So in future this concept can make great revolution in the field of embedded systems Usually we use to see the cost of all electronic goods are reducing gradually except the automation devices like Robots and satellites and etc, by using this idea we can over come from all this defects. So surely this technique can be implemented in future not only for industrial purpose, but also in fields of defense security, Space research, embedded electronics and etc.....,

VI. CONCLUSION

Thus, the thermal characteristics and the power handling capability analysis of the all-silicon dielectric-block MEMS phase shifter concept have been evaluated and compared with two conventional true-time-delay and DMTL phase-shifter concepts, which utilized the air-suspended thin gold membrane. The peak-temperature rise due to the high signal power at 75 GHz of the novel dielectric-block phase shifter is only 30 °C or even lesser at 40 dBm, which is 10 and 20 times lower than the conventional MEMS phase-shifter concepts, respectively. And power consumption can reduce drastically by implementing this technique, which in future can face all power demands. This can create huge revolution in the fields of electronics and embedded devices production, with lesser cost so every one can afford all sort of upcoming devices

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